
THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE 8TH GRADE ALGEBRA LESSON TO INCREASE STUDENTS’ INTEREST IN THE LESSON

Jabborova Gulasal Sultanovna

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute, teacher of the "Exact Sciences" department

gulasaljabborova96@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3920-790X>

Abstract: It is difficult and complicated to imagine today without the Internet and information technologies. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the interest of students in all aspects of the lesson, especially in school lessons, every subject teacher should use the achievements of information technology in his specialty. This is important for both the teacher and the student. As a reason, it can be said that for the teacher, if he learns new methods in his specialty, it will serve for students to become a competitive staff in the future and to quickly and easily learn new views in their field.

Keywords: Mathematics, information technology, artificial intelligence, internet, algebra, high school, trigonometric function.

Programmed educational tools are a didactic tool designed for partial or complete automation of the educational process with the help of computer technologies. They are one of the promising forms of increasing the efficiency of the educational process, and are used as teaching tools of modern technologies. Pedagogical programmed tools are created using programs that implement effects such as dynamic illustrations, sound processes, 3D animations.

In the educational system, serious attention is paid to such important tasks as the introduction and use of modern information technologies, software educational tools, the full satisfaction of students' information needs, access to the world information community, and the creation of favorable conditions for the use of information resources. being directed.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems. These processes include learning (the acquisition of information and rules for using that information), reasoning (using rules to reach approximate or definite conclusions), and self-correction. AI encompasses a broad range of technologies and applications, from basic calculations to self-driving cars and sophisticated robotics. The ultimate goal of AI is to create systems that can perform tasks that would normally require human intelligence.

Here are several examples of how artificial intelligence is being used in the teaching process:

1. **Personalized Learning:** AI algorithms can analyze student data to create personalized learning paths, adapting content and pacing to individual needs and learning styles.

2. **Intelligent Tutoring Systems:** These systems use AI to provide personalized tutoring and feedback to students, helping them master concepts at their own pace.

3. **Automated Grading:** AI-powered tools can grade assignments, quizzes, and exams quickly and accurately, freeing up teachers' time for other tasks.

4. **Virtual Assistants:** AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants can provide students with instant help and support, answering questions and guiding them through course materials.

5. **Adaptive Learning Platforms:** AI can analyze student performance data to identify areas of weakness and provide targeted interventions and resources to help students improve.

6. **Natural Language Processing (NLP):** NLP algorithms can analyze and understand students' written responses, providing feedback on grammar, style, and content.

7. **Content Creation:** AI can generate educational content, such as quizzes, practice exercises, and lesson plans, based on curriculum standards and learning objectives.

8. **Data Analytics:** AI algorithms can analyze large datasets to identify trends and patterns in student performance, helping teachers make data-driven decisions to improve instruction.

These are just a few examples, and the use of AI in education continues to evolve and expand as technology advances.

Today, we can use artificial intelligence technologies in the teaching of school mathematics courses. Let's look at the example of a student. That is, nowadays mathematics is considered a difficult subject among students, but actually mathematics is an interesting and interesting subject. One of the main problems of mathematics being considered difficult is that the students did not master the topics well or were not paying attention in the lesson. As a result, they have difficulty completing homework assignments and the idea that mathematics is a difficult subject is imprinted in their minds. In order to prevent this, it is necessary and necessary to teach students the use of artificial intelligence technologies. How can this be done?

In secondary schools, we face this problem less often in primary classes. For this purpose, let's look at the example of upper classes. Traditional teaching methods alone will not be enough to explain the topics in the textbooks created for upper

grades. Therefore, we use the graphs of trigonometric functions to solve some problems related to drawing the graphs of trigonometric functions given in the textbooks of the 8th grade. we draw with the help of artificial intelligence.

The teacher goes to the students from the chapter "Trigonometric functions and trigonometric inequality" to topic 5 "Making the graph of a trigonometric function" and gives definitions and theorems related to it $y=\sin x, y=\cos x, y=\tan x$ and $y=\cot x$ explained how to draw a graph of functions and how to implement them in sequence. But as a result of the student's inattention or forgetfulness, it is difficult to do homework. In this situation, the reader can find the answer to the question he is interested in by referring to AI.

A reader can quickly find an answer by asking SI how to find the graph of a trigonometric function. This can be done in the following way. For example, from artificial intelligence "in what sequence is the graph of the trigonometric function performed?" When we asked, he told us how to draw the graph of a function consisting of the following sequence:

Drawing trigonometric functions can be a fun and educational activity! Here are some general steps to draw the graphs of trigonometric functions:

1. Understand the Function: First, understand the basic shape of the trigonometric function you want to draw. For example, the sine function oscillates between -1 and 1 and has a period of 2π .

2. Determine the Domain and Range: Determine the domain (the values of x) for which you want to draw the graph, as well as the range (the values of y).

3. Choose an Appropriate Scale: Decide on the scale for your axes based on the domain and range. For trigonometric functions, a common scale for the x -axis is in terms of π (e.g., $\pi/2, \pi, 3\pi/2$, etc.).

4. Plot Key Points: Plot key points on the graph. For trigonometric functions, these points often include the maximum and minimum values, points where the function crosses the axes, and points where the function has special properties (e.g., intercepts, points of inflection).

5. Draw the Graph: Connect the plotted points smoothly to create the graph of the function. Pay attention to the shape and behavior of the function, such as its periodicity, symmetry, and any asymptotes.

6. Label the Axes and Graph: Label the axes with appropriate values and give your graph a title. You may also want to label key points or features of the graph to provide context.

7. Repeat for Other Trigonometric Functions: Repeat the process for other trigonometric functions, such as cosine, tangent, secant, cosecant, and cotangent.

Remember to practice and experiment with different scales and ranges to gain a better understanding of how trigonometric functions behave. You can also use

graphing software or online graphing tools to help you visualize the functions more accurately.

In this way, the graph of the trigonometric function can be drawn. In the process of drawing a graph, students can also use computer programs or mathematical graphing tools.

Through the above, the reader will get information about how to draw the graph of the trigonometric function. Through this, the student can independently complete the task given at home without difficulty.

To draw the graph of $y = \sin(x)$, follow these steps:

1. Understand the Function: The sine function oscillates between -1 and 1, repeating every 2π radians.

2. Determine the Domain and Range: The domain of $\sin(x)$ is all real numbers, and the range is between -1 and 1.

3. Choose an Appropriate Scale: For the x-axis, you might use values like $-\pi$, $-\pi/2$, 0, $\pi/2$, π , $3\pi/2$, 2π , etc. For the y-axis, you'll want to include values between -1 and 1.

4. Plot Key Points: Key points to plot include:

- (0,0) - the origin
- $(\pi/2, 1)$ - where $\sin(x)$ reaches its maximum value
- $(\pi, 0)$ - a point of inflection
- $(3\pi/2, -1)$ - where $\sin(x)$ reaches its minimum value
- $(2\pi, 0)$ - another point of inflection

5. Draw the Graph: Connect the plotted points with a smooth curve. Since $\sin(x)$ is a periodic function, the graph should repeat the same shape every 2π units.

6. Label the Axes and Graph: Label the x-axis with appropriate values and the y-axis with values between -1 and 1. Give your graph a title, like "Graph of $y = \sin(x)$ ".

7. Optional: You can extend the graph beyond 2π to show more repetitions of the function.

By following these steps, students will be able to accurately draw the graph of $y = \sin(x)$. Also, the graph of the function $y = \cos x$ is drawn similar to the graph of the function $y = \sin x$.

To draw the graph of $y = \tan(x)$, you can follow these steps:

1. Understanding the Function: The tangent function has vertical asymptotes at odd multiples of $\pi/2$ and repeats every π radians.

2. Determining the Domain and Range: The domain of $\tan(x)$ is all real numbers except odd multiples of $\pi/2$, and the range is all real numbers.

3. Selecting Appropriate Scale: Students can choose values like $-\pi/2$, $-\pi/4$, 0, $\pi/4$, $\pi/2$, π , $3\pi/2$, 2π for the x-axis and appropriate values for the y-axis.

4. Plotting Key Points: Plot the key points:

- $(-\pi/4, -1)$ and $(\pi/4, 1)$ - initial points
- $(0, 0)$ - point where the function crosses the x-axis
- $(-\pi/2, \text{undefined})$ and $(\pi/2, \text{undefined})$ - vertical asymptotes

5. Drawing the Graph: Connect these points with a smooth curve. The graph will repeat every π units.

6. Labeling Axes and the Graph: Label the x-axis with appropriate values and the y-axis with appropriate values. Provide a title for the graph, such as "Graph of $y = \tan(x)$ ".

7. Additional Steps: Students can extend the graph beyond 2π to show more cycles.

Following these steps will help students accurately draw the graph of $y = \tan(x)$. Keep in mind that it's important to pay attention to the vertical asymptotes and the behavior around those points when drawing the graph of $y = \tan(x)$. Also, the graph of the function $y = \cot(x)$ is drawn similar to the graph of the function $y = \tan(x)$.

Graphing trigonometric functions in Desmos is quite straightforward. Here are the steps to graph a trigonometric function in Desmos:

1. Open Desmos: Go to the Desmos website or open the Desmos app.

2. Enter the Function: In the input bar, type the trigonometric function student want to graph. For example, if students want to graph the sine function $y = \sin(x)$, you would type " $y = \sin(x)$ ".

3. View the Graph: As students type, Desmos will automatically generate the graph based on what you've entered. Students should see the graph of the trigonometric function appear on the screen.

4. Adjustments: Students can make adjustments to the graph by zooming in or out, panning, or changing the window settings to see different parts of the graph.

5. Multiple Functions: If students want to graph multiple trigonometric functions on the same set of axes, students can simply enter each function separated by a comma. For example, entering " $y = \sin(x), y = \cos(x)$ " will graph both the sine and cosine functions on the same set of axes.

6. Customization: Desmos allows for extensive customization of graphs. Students can change colors, add labels, plot points, and more to enhance the visualization.

By following these steps, students can easily graph trigonometric functions in Desmos and explore their behavior visually.

To graph the function $y = \sin(x)$ in Desmos, you can follow these steps:

1. Open Desmos: Go to the Desmos website or open the Desmos app.

2. Enter the Function: In the input bar, type " $y = \sin(x)$ ".

3. View the Graph: Desmos will automatically generate the graph of $y = \sin(x)$ based on what you've entered. You should see the graph of the sine function appear on the screen(1-rasm).

By following these steps, students can easily graph the sine function $y = \sin(x)$ in Desmos and explore its behavior visually.

Picture 1. The graph of the $y=\sin x$ function in the Demos program.

To graph the function $y = (x)$ in Desmos, you can follow these steps:

1. Open Desmos: Go to the Desmos website or open the Desmos app.
2. Enter the Function: In the input bar, type " $y = \cot(x)$ ".

3. View the Graph: Desmos will automatically generate the graph of $y = (x)$ based on what you've entered. Students should see the graph appear on the screen (2-rasm).

Picture 2. The graph of the $y=\cot x$ function in the Demos program.

Conclusion. In short, artificial intelligence technologies are used in every field. The use of the above technologies, including in the field of general secondary education,

arouses students' interest in science. We believe that this will help them grow into mature people in the future and find their place in society [2-15].

References:

1. Algebra. Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktablari uchun 9- sinf darslik/ Sh. A. Alimov, Sh. N. Usmonov, O. R. Xolmuhammedov, M. A. Mirzaahmedov T.: : “O‘qituvchi” MNIU. 2019. – 240 b
2. Jabborova, G. S. (2022). Vektor fazolarda operatorlar va ularning asosiy xossalari haqida. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 17-32.
3. Jabborova G.S. Hayitova X.G‘. (2023)“Uchburchakli panjarada aniqlangan diskret Shryodinger operatorining xossalari” *Tadqiqotlar jahon ilmiy – metodik jurnali*, 6(14), 118-126.
4. Rustamovich, M. U. (2023). Comparative Analysis of 6th Grade Natural Science Textbooks of Uzbekistan and Turkey. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(3), 114-120.
5. Mustafoyev O‘.R. 6-sinf "Tabiiy fan" darsligida namoyishli tajribalarning o'rni va roli//*Innovations in technology and science education* 2:17 (2023),p. 253-261.
6. Daminov M.I., Mustafoyev O‘.R. Fizikadan maktab o‘quvchilari uchun zamonaviy darsliklar yaratishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish//ta’lim sifatini oshirish: muammo, yechim va istiqbol1:1(2020), p. 683-685.
7. Даминов М.И., Каххоров С.К. и Мустафаев У.Р. (2020). Изучение основ нанотехнологий в школьной программе физика. *Научные доклады Бухарского государственного университета*, 3 (4), 320-324.
8. Mustafoyev O‘. R. (2024). Maktab fizika darslarida o‘quvchilar faolligini oshirishda Sun’iy intellektning o‘rni. *Pedagogik akmeologiya*, 2(10), 218-221.
9. Daminov M. I. Mustafoyev O‘. R. (2024). Maktab fizika ta’limida sun’iy intellektidan foydalanish bo‘yicha xorij tajribasi va asosiy yo‘nalishlar. *Fan, ta’lim va innovatsiyalar: nazariya, amaliyot, natijalar*, 1(1), 578-582.
10. Mustafoyev O‘. R. (2024). Sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida O‘quvchilarning o‘quv faoliyatini faollashtirishning shakl, metod va vositalari. *Fan, ta’lim va innovatsiyalar: nazariya, amaliyot, natijalar*, 1(1), 272-275.
11. Mustafoyev O‘. R. (2024). 10 – sinf fizika darslarida o‘quvchilarni faollashtirishida sun’iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish. *Pedagogik mahorat*, 1(5), 134-137.
12. A. Sh. Rashidov Matematika darslarida ta’limning shaxsga yo ‘naltirilgan texnologiyasi. *Центр научных публикаций*. 2021 yil. 3-son. 68-72 bet

13. A.Sh. Rashidov Ijtimoiy-gumanitar ta’lim yo’nalishi talabalari uchun matematik fanlar bo’yicha amaliy mashg’ulotlarni o’tkazish. Science and Education №9. С 283-291

14. О.О.Халлоқова. А.Рашидов Пороговое собственное значение модели Фридрикса. Молодой ученый, 2015 №15. С. 1-3

15. A. Sh. Rashidov Interaktivnyye metody pri izuchenii temy "Opredelennyuy integral i yego prilozheniya". Nauchnyye issledovaniya. № 34:3. С 21-24